

Effects of Peer Teaching and Inquiry Teaching Strategies on Achievement of Mathematics Students in Delta Central Senatorial District

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the effects of Peer Teaching (PT) and Inquiry-Based Teaching (IBT) strategies on the academic achievement of mathematics students in Delta Central Senatorial District. Four research questions were raised, and corresponding hypotheses were stated and tested at the 0.05 level of significance. The study employed a quasi-experimental, non-equivalent pre-test, post-test control group design. The population comprised 21,147 Senior Secondary II students from 190 public secondary schools during the 2024/2025 session. A sample of 392 students was selected from six mixed secondary schools using a multistage sampling technique. The Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT) was the instrument used for data collection. Its reliability was established by administering it to 50 SS II students in two secondary schools outside the study area, yielding a reliability coefficient of 0.81 using the Kuder-Richardson Formula 21. Both pre-test and post-test scores were collected and analyzed. Descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) were used to answer research questions, while inferential statistics (t-test, ANOVA, and ANCOVA) were used to test the hypotheses. Findings shows a significant difference in mean achievement scores among the instructional groups, with students taught using Peer Teaching achieving higher scores than those taught through Inquiry-Based Teaching and those in the control group. However, there were no significant differences in achievement between male and female students, under Peer Teaching or Inquiry-Based Teaching strategies. Additionally, there were no significant interaction effects between instructional strategy and sex or location on students' mathematics achievement. Based on these findings, it was recommended that mathematics teachers incorporate these strategies—particularly peer teaching into their instructional practices to encourage active learning and peer collaboration.

Introduction

Mathematics is a fundamental field of study that deals with numbers, quantities, shapes, patterns, and relationships. It's a subject that is essential for understanding the world around us, making informed decisions, and solving various problems. Mathematics is used in various disciplines, industries, and everyday life. Mathematics teaches critical thinking and problem-solving skills that can be applied to various situations. Mathematics is present in everyday activities like budgeting, cooking, shopping, and measuring. Thus, the importance of mathematics in every sphere of human life cannot be overemphasized (Bal & Seekin-Kapucu, 2022). According to Akpokiniovo (2022), students' lack of interest in learning physics and mathematics leads to poor academic achievement in the subject and a shortage of human resources in key professions. Consequently, there is a low number of students who qualify for enrollment into mathematics in higher institutions of learning within Nigeria and some other underdeveloped nations. Conscious efforts are needed to prepare learners who will be useful and qualified to pursue important mathematics -oriented courses at the higher education level by capturing and sustaining their interest during mathematics instruction.

In order to achieve the objectives of mathematics education, there is need for better academic achievement among students. Therefore, the importance of mathematics in almost all the facet of life endeavours cannot be over-emphasized. Poor academic achievement not only leads to a negative image of the student, but it also puts an enormous strain on the parents. Given the dynamic role mathematics plays in any society, as discussed above, it is quite appalling and unfortunate to see students fail mathematics examinations (Nshimiyimana & Cartledge, 2020). This gloomy condition has prompted a slew of research initiatives over the years aimed at determining the elements that contribute to low academic achievement in mathematics and what steps may be taken to ameliorate the situation. As a result, several variables interact to determine students' academic achievement. However, the researcher believes that instructional strategies can have an impact on students' mathematics academic achievement. Instructional strategies are a crucial component of effective teaching, and they can significantly impact students' learning outcomes in any subject, including mathematics. Effective instructional strategies can make mathematics more engaging and intriguing for students. When students are actively involved in

the learning process and find the material relevant, they are more likely to be motivated to learn and perform better academically. Among the different instructional strategies that exist, the researcher is also of the opinion that peer teaching strategies (PTS) and inquiry-based teaching (IBT) could be effective strategies for enhancing students' academic achievement in mathematics.

Peer Teaching Strategy (PTS) is an educational approach in which students teach and learn from their peers. The Peer Teaching Strategy (PTS) is an instructional approach that actively engages students in the teaching and learning process through four key steps. It begins with individual reflection, where students independently engage with the lesson content, allowing them to form initial ideas, identify areas of confusion, and develop personal insights (Akpokiniovo & Akudolu, 2023). This is followed by peer discussion, during which students collaborate in pairs or small groups to share their understandings, clarify concepts, and challenge each other's viewpoints. Through this interaction, learners gain new perspectives and enhance their critical thinking skills. A study by Uyim, and Nonye (2019) emphasized that students learn better when actively involved in the teaching-learning process. It also agrees with findings by Osondu (2021) who reported that the use of learner-centred methods such as peer-teaching and inquiry-based approaches significantly improve students' academic achievement in mathematics. Despite the fact that there are several examples of student-centred approaches, this research only looked at guided inquiry teaching and peer tutoring strategies.

Inquiry method can simply be defined as a form of active learning that starts by posing questions, problems or scenarios rather than simply presenting established facts or portraying a smooth path to knowledge. The process is often assisted by a facilitator. There are many different explanations for inquiry teaching and learning and the various levels of inquiry that can exist within various contents. Bandi and Bell (2008) clearly outline four levels of inquiry.

Level 1: Confirmation Inquiry; the teacher has taught a particular topic. The teacher then develops questions and a procedure that guides students through an activity. This method is enables the teacher to reinforce concepts taught and to introduce students into learning to follow procedures, collect and record data correctly and to confirm and deepen understanding.

Level 2: Structured Inquiry; the teacher provides the initial question and an outline of the procedure. Students are to formulate explanations of their findings through evaluating and analyzing the data that they collect.

Level 3: Guided Inquiry; the teacher provides only the research questions for the students. The students are responsible for designing and following their own procedures to test the question and then communicate their results and findings.

Level 4: Open/True Inquiry; Students formulate their own research questions, design and follow through with a developed procedure, and communicate their findings and results. This type of inquiry is often seen in science fair contexts where students drive their own investigative questions.

The goal of the inquiry-based teaching strategy, according to Mwenda and Ndayambaje (2021), is to foster curiosity, critical thinking, problem-solving skills, and a deeper understanding of the subject matter. Bako (2020) described inquiry-based teaching (IBT) as a student-centred approach that emphasises exploration, investigation, and problem solving. In this approach, students are encouraged to ask questions, make predictions, and engage in hands-on activities to discover mathematical concepts. By actively exploring mathematical ideas, students develop a deeper understanding of the underlying principles and are better able to apply their knowledge in real-world situations. Numerous studies (Issaka, 2020; Mehboob et al., 2021) have highlighted the benefits of inquiry-based teaching on students' achievement. For instance, a meta-analysis conducted by Hiebert et al. (2012) revealed that students who received inquiry-based instruction performed significantly better on assessments compared to those who did not receive inquiry-based instruction. Some researchers such as Jacinta (2011) conducted a study on inquiry method and students' academic achievement in biology in Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni Local Government Area of Rivers State, Nigeria. The author shows that inquiry method has a significant effect on students' achievements in biology.

The effects of peer-teaching (PT) and inquiry-based teaching (IBT) strategies on students' achievement may differ depending on sex. A student's sex could be male or female. The term "sex" refers to the biological characteristics of being male or female. Sex can influence various aspects of human life, including educational outcomes, where differences may emerge in how males and females respond to certain teaching methods. When comparing the effects of these teaching methods across sexes, some studies (Bello & Johnson, 2020; Adewale & Smith, 2019) found no evidence of a significant relationship between sex and achievement when exposed to inquiry and guided-discovery instructional methods respectively. However, others (Nguyen & Taylor, 2021;

Li & Wang, 2022; Macaulay & Obafemi, 2022) found a substantial relationship between sex and achievement, with males scoring higher than females when instructional methods such as Simulation instructional strategy and Teacher-demonstration method and guided inquiry were used. There are mixed results from reviewed empirical studies on the effects of guided inquiry teaching and peer tutoring strategies on students' achievement, however, the gender effect on the aspect of students need to be examined. As a result, the findings of this study will provide additional empirical evidence on this topic. It should be noted that gender is a intervening variable in this study. Against this background, therefore, this study sought to examine the comparative effect of inquiry and peer tutoring teaching strategies on the achievement of mathematics students in in Delta Central Senatorial District.

Statement of the Problem

Mathematics is a fundamental subject that plays a critical role in students' academic and career development. However, students' academic achievement in mathematics has remained consistently low, as indicated by poor results in external examinations. Many students struggle with fundamental mathematical concepts, leading to a lack of confidence, negative attitudes toward the subject, and high failure rates. For instance, the results released by WAEC in 2022 revealed that a high number of the candidates that sat for the examination failed mathematics (WAEC Chief Examiner, 2022). A similar trend was observed in the 2023 released West Africa Senior School Certificate Examination (WAEC) results by the West Africa Examination Council, which declared that a few of the candidates were successful in five subjects including mathematics (WAEC Chief Examiner, 2023). The fluctuation in students' academic achievement in the subject may be as a result of rote learning of mathematics, which occurs due to lack of active involvement in the teaching of the subject.

Thus, student's poor academic achievement at the secondary school has been attributed to ineffective methods and strategies used by teachers in teaching the subject. The available literature on methods of teaching in science education suggests the need to employ new and innovative teaching strategy. The researcher therefore in this study is of the opinion that the use of Peer teaching (PT) and Inquiry-based teaching (IBT) strategies may enhance the academic achievement of students in mathematics. The problem of the study, therefore, is will the application of Peer-

Teaching (PT) and Inquiry-Based Teaching (IBT) strategies produce differential effect on academic achievement of students in mathematics in Delta Central Senatorial District?

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the difference in mean achievement score of mathematics students taught using peer-teaching (PT) and inquiry-based teaching (IBT) strategies in Delta Central Senatorial District?
2. What is the difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught mathematics using peer-teaching (PT) strategy in Delta Central Senatorial District?
3. What is the difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught mathematics using inquiry-based teaching (IBT) strategy in Delta Central Senatorial District?
4. What is the interaction effect of instructional strategies and sex on mathematics students' achievement in Delta Central Senatorial District?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses are formulated for the study and were tested at 0.05 level of significance

1. There is no significant difference in mean achievement score of mathematics students taught using Peer-Teaching (PT) and Inquiry-Based Teaching (IBT) strategies in Delta Central Senatorial District.
2. There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught mathematics using Peer-Teaching (PT) strategy in Delta Central Senatorial District.
3. There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught mathematics using Inquiry-Based Teaching (IBT) strategy in Delta Central Senatorial District.
4. There is no significant effect of interaction of instructional strategy and sex on mathematics students' achievement in Delta Central Senatorial District.

Research Methodology

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This study employed quasi-experimental non-randomized pretest posttest control group design. There was no randomization of subjects in this study. Intact classes were randomly assigned to the experimental and control groups. The independent variables are Instructional methods. The dependent variable is the achievement score of mathematics students. The population for this study comprised a total of 21,147 Senior Secondary School Two (SS II) students across 190 public secondary schools in Delta Central Senatorial District, Delta State, during the 2024/2025 session. A sample of 392 SSII students selected from six (6) public mixed senior secondary schools in Delta Central Senatorial District made up the sample size for this study. The six (6) public mixed senior secondary schools were selected using simple random sampling technique.

The instrument that was used for the study is the Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT). The MAT was used to measure academic achievement. The MAT consists of two sections. Section A contained instruction on the student's bio-data (sex and location). Section B consists of 50 multiple-choice questions that will be adapted from past West African Examination Council (WAEC) questions in line with the selected concept or topic that will be treated in the study. The concept that made up the MAT are Logarithm and indices, Approximations, Sequence and Series, Quadratic Equations, Gradient of a Curve and Algebraic Fractions. The instrument was tested for reliability in two secondary schools in Delta South Senatorial District. While carrying out the reliability test the instrument was administered on 50 SS II students from schools outside the research area. The Kuder-Richardson formula -21 was used to compute the reliability index of data collected, which yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.81

The treatment procedure began with the allocation of instructional methods to schools. Two instructional methods were assigned to four intact classes selected from both urban and rural areas—one from each sampled school. To assign the treatment methods, the two instructional strategies and the control group were written on paper and coded as follows: Peer Teaching Strategy (PTS), Inquiry-Based Teaching Strategy (IBTS), and Control Group (CG). Six equal-sized sheets of paper were labeled PTS1, PTS2, IBTS1, IBTS2, CG1, and CG2, then ruffled and placed in a container. Six teachers each selected one sheet of paper, with replacement. Teachers who picked PTS were assigned to use the peer teaching strategy, those who picked IBTS were assigned to use the inquiry-based teaching strategy, and those who picked CG were assigned to the control group. This process ensured that two intact classes—one from an urban school and one

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from a rural school—were assigned to each treatment method. The next phase involved training the research assistants. The four mathematics instructors designated to use the peer teaching and inquiry-based teaching strategies were trained before the treatment began. The training lasted four days, with 40-minute sessions each day. Alongside two other experts, the researcher conducted the training, focusing on the effective use of each instructional strategy. The first day was used to explore the characteristics of both teaching strategies.

On the second day, the teachers were trained using manuals adapted from Muştu and Tekin (2021) and Assem (2018), with separate manuals for peer teaching and inquiry-based strategies. Each group of teachers was trained separately by different resource persons. The training highlighted the steps and stages involved in using each strategy, as well as the specific roles of teachers and students during instruction. The third and fourth days focused on practice and idea generation for applying each instructional strategy to the chosen mathematics concepts. The training concluded when the facilitators were confident that the teachers could effectively implement the strategies during instruction.

The final phase was the actual implementation of the treatment. This occurred in three stages. In the first stage, pretests using the Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT) were administered to all the groups after obtaining permission from school authorities. The pretest results were used to assess the equivalence of the groups and to identify any initial differences that could be attributed to the treatment.

Stage Two: In the second stage, lesson plans covering six weeks of instruction were given to the research assistants one week before treatment commenced. The lesson plans detailed the activities of both teachers and students during each class session.

Stage Three: In the third Stage, teachers in each selected group will presented the content of the topics that were selected to the students with the use of peer teaching strategy and inquiry based teaching strategy in their various school for six weeks. Teachers instructed the students during the treatment session, adhering to the procedures they learned about during their training. In the treatment, the teacher in the control group only gave the selected topics to the students in the form of revision using past examination questions, without applying any specific instructional treatment method.

Stage Four: At the end of the six weeks of instruction by the teacher, a post-test was given to the students in all the groups.

The research questions were analysed using Mean Scores and Standard Deviation scores. Hypotheses were tested with t-test statistics, One-way Analysis of variance, Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA). All hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

Results and Discussion

The results are tabulated, interpreted and discussed immediately after the research questions and corresponding hypothesis.

Research Question One

What is the difference in mean achievement score of mathematics students taught using peer-teaching (PT) and inquiry-based teaching (IBT) strategies in Delta Central Senatorial District?

Table 1: Comparison of The Mean(\bar{x}) achievement pretest score of mathematics students taught using peer-teaching (PT) and inquiry-based teaching (IBT) strategies in Delta Central Senatorial District

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Peer Teaching Method	196	11.22	1.26
Inquiry-Based Teaching Method	152	11.16	1.77
Control Group	44	11.64	1.42
Total	392	11.24	1.49

Table 1 revealed the mean and standard deviation of the achievement scores of mathematics students taught using peer-teaching and inquiry-based teaching instructional strategies. In the table, the means of the pretest scores of students taught using peer-teaching and inquiry-based teaching strategies are 11.16 and 11.14, with standard deviations of 1.33 and 1.69, respectively. The mean difference in the pretest scores between the two instructional methods is 0.02.

Analysis of variance(ANOVA) was further used to find out whether the mean difference is significant and presented in Table 2

Table 2: ANOVA Comparing the Mean Achievement Pretest Score of mathematics students taught using peer-teaching (PT) and inquiry-based teaching (IBT) strategies in Delta Central Senatorial District

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	7.853	2	3.927	1.767	.172
Within Groups	864.636	389	2.223		
Total	872.490	391			

Table 2 shows that the ANOVA comparison of the pretest scores of mathematics students taught using peer teaching and inquiry-based teaching instructional strategies is not significant ($F = 1.767$, $p \geq 0.05$). This implies that the students were similar in terms of their prior knowledge of the mathematics concepts before the instructional strategies were applied.

Table 3: Comparison of The Mean(\bar{x}) achievement posttest score of mathematics students taught using peer-teaching (PT) and inquiry-based teaching (IBT) strategies in Delta Central Senatorial District

Instructional methods	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Peer Teaching Method	196	44.80	9.428
Inquiry-Based Teaching Method	152	40.95	9.088
Control Group	44	26.30	8.157
Total	392	41.23	10.726

Table 3 shows the mean and standard deviation of the posttest achievement scores of mathematics students taught using peer teaching and inquiry-based teaching instructional strategies. In the table, the means of the posttest scores for students taught using peer-teaching and inquiry-based teaching strategies are 45.21 and 41.19, with standard deviations of 9.40 and 8.92, respectively. The mean difference in the posttest scores between the two instructional methods is 4.02. Analysis of variance(ANOVA) was further used to find out whether the mean difference is significant and presented in Table 4.

Hypothesis One: There is no significant difference in mean achievement score of mathematics students taught using peer teaching (PT) and inquiry-based teaching (IBT) strategies in Delta Central Senatorial District.

Table 4: ANOVA Comparing the Mean Achievement Score of difference in Mean Achievement Score of Mathematics Students taught using Peer-Teaching (PT) And Inquiry-Based Teaching (IBT) Strategies in Delta Central Senatorial District

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	12318.219	2	6159.109	73.348	.000
Within Groups	32664.575	389	83.971		
Total	44982.793	391			

Table 4 shows that the ANOVA comparison of the posttest achievement scores of mathematics students taught using peer-teaching and inquiry-based teaching instructional strategies is significant ($F = 73.348, p = 0.000$). Therefore, the null hypothesis, which states that there is no significant difference in mean achievement score of mathematics students taught using peer teaching (PT) and inquiry-based teaching (IBT) strategies in Delta Central Senatorial District was rejected. This implies that there is a significant difference in the mean achievement scores of mathematics students taught using the two instructional strategies, in favour of students taught using peer teaching (PT) strategy.

To determine the direction of the significant difference observed in this hypothesis, the post hoc analysis using Scheffe test was computed as shown in Table 5

Table 5

Scheffe Post – Hoc Test Determine the Direction of Difference Among the Groups

(I) Instructional methods	(J) Instructional methods	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.
Peer Teaching Method	Inquiry-Based Teaching Method	3.849*	.990	.001
	Control Group	18.500*	1.529	.000
Inquiry-Based Teaching Method	Peer Teaching Method	-3.849*	.990	.001
	Control Group	14.652*	1.569	.000
Control Group	Peer Teaching Method	-18.500*	1.529	.000
	Inquiry-Based Teaching Method	-14.652*	1.569	.000

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Table 5 shows the post hoc Scheffe test results, which determine which specific instructional methods significantly differ from one another after an overall significant difference was detected via ANOVA. The post hoc analysis shows a clear hierarchy in instructional effectiveness: Peer Teaching Method > Inquiry-Based Teaching Method > Control Group. This suggests that using peer teaching strategy results in the highest student achievement, followed by inquiry-based methods, with the control group performing the lowest.

Research Question Two

What is the difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught mathematics using peer-teaching (PT) strategy in Delta Central Senatorial District?

Table 6: Comparison Between the Mean(\bar{x}) mean achievement scores of male and female students taught mathematics using peer-teaching (PT) strategy in Delta Central Senatorial District.

sex	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean difference
Male	91	46.11	8.82	2.45
Female	105	43.66	9.83	

Table 6 shows the mean and standard deviation of the achievement scores of male and female students taught mathematics using the peer-teaching instructional strategy. In the table, the means of the achievement scores for male and female students are 46.11 and 43.66, with standard deviations of 8.82 and 9.83, respectively. The mean difference in the achievement scores between male and female students is 2.45. To find out whether the mean difference was significant, H_{03} was tested with t-test and presented in Table 7

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught mathematics using peer teaching (PT) strategy in Delta Central Senatorial District.

Table 7: t-test comparing the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught mathematics using peer-teaching (PT) strategy in Delta Central Senatorial District.

Sex	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	df	t-cal.	Sig. (2-tailed)	Decision
Males	91	46.11	8.82	194	1.83	.069	Null hypothesis not rejected
females	105	43.66	9.83				

Table 7 shows that the t-test comparison of the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught mathematics using the peer teaching strategy is not significant ($t = 1.83, p = 0.069$). Therefore, the null hypothesis, which states that there is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female students, was not rejected. This implies that there is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught mathematics using the peer teaching strategy in Delta Central Senatorial District.

Research Question Three: What is the difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught mathematics using inquiry-based teaching (IBT) strategy in Delta Central Senatorial District?

Table 8: Comparison Between the Mean(\bar{x}) achievement scores of male and female students taught mathematics using inquiry-based teaching (IBT) strategy in Delta Central Senatorial District

Sex	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean difference
Male	86	41.45	9.671	1.36
Female	66	40.29	8.294	

Table 8 shows the mean and standard deviation of the achievement scores of male and female students taught mathematics using the inquiry-based teaching instructional strategy. In the table, the means of the achievement scores for male and female students are 41.79 and 40.43, with standard deviations of 9.43 and 8.22, respectively. The mean difference in the achievement scores between male and female students is 1.36. To find out whether the mean difference was significant, H_{04} was tested with t-test and presented in Table 9.

Hypothesis Three: There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of urban and rural students taught mathematics using Peer Teaching (PT) strategy in Delta Central Senatorial District.

Table 10: t-test comparing the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught mathematics using peer-teaching (PT) strategy in Delta Central Senatorial District.

Sex	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	df	t-cal.	Sig. (2-tailed)	Decision
Male	86	41.45	9.671	150	.783	.435	Null hypothesis not rejected
Female	66	40.29	8.294				

Table 10 shows that the t-test comparison of the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught mathematics using the inquiry-based teaching strategy is not significant ($t = 0.783, p = 0.435$). Therefore, the null hypothesis, which states that there is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female students, was not rejected. This implies that there is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught mathematics using the inquiry-based teaching strategy in Delta Central Senatorial District.

Research Question Four: What is the interaction effect of instructional strategies and sex on mathematics students’ achievement in Delta Central Senatorial District?

Table 11: Means(X) and Standard Deviations (SD) analysis of the interaction effect of instructional strategies and sex on mathematics students’ achievement in Delta Central Senatorial District

Instructional methods	sex	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Peer Teaching Method	Male	91	46.11	8.82
	Female	105	43.66	9.83
Inquiry-Based Teaching Method	Male	86	41.45	9.67
	Female	66	40.29	8.29
Control Group	Male	22	28.27	7.81
	Female	22	24.32	8.19
Total	Male	199	42.13	10.52
	Female	193	40.30	10.88

Table 11 shows the Means (X) and Standard Deviations (SD) analysis of the interaction effect of instructional strategies and sex on mathematics students’ achievement in Delta Central Senatorial District. For students taught using the Peer Teaching Method, the mean scores for male and female students are 46.11 and 43.66, with standard deviations of 8.82 and 9.83, respectively. For those taught using the Inquiry-Based Teaching Method, the mean scores for male and female

students are 41.45 and 40.29, with standard deviations of 9.67 and 8.29, respectively. In the Control Group, the mean scores for male and female students are 28.27 and 24.32, with standard deviations of 7.81 and 8.19, respectively. The results suggest a noticeable interaction effect between instructional strategy and sex, as male students consistently scored higher than their female counterparts across all groups. To find out whether the mean is significant interaction effect, H_{06} was tested with ANCOVA and presented in Table 12.

Hypothesis Four: There is no significant interaction effect of instructional strategies and sex on mathematics students’ achievement in Delta Central Senatorial District?

Table 12: ANCOVA of the interaction effect of instructional strategies and sex on mathematics students’ achievement in Delta Central Senatorial District

Tests of Between-Subjects Effects					
Dependent Variable: Posttest					
Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	12838.569 ^a	6	2139.762	25.628	.000
Intercept	8677.109	1	8677.109	103.928	.000
Pretest	4.315	1	4.315	.052	.820
Instructional methods	12391.830	2	6195.915	74.210	.000
sex	405.734	1	405.734	4.860	.028
Instructional methods * sex	77.389	2	38.695	.463	.629
Error	32144.224	385	83.491		
Total	711253.000	392			
Corrected Total	44982.793	391			

a. R Squared = .285 (Adjusted R Squared = .274)

Table 12 shows the ANCOVA of the interaction effect of instructional strategies and sex on students’ academic achievement in mathematics. The computed F-ratio for the interaction effect, that is, $F(2, 385) = 0.463$ with a p-value of 0.629. Testing the null hypothesis at an alpha level of 0.05, the p-value of 0.540 was greater than the alpha level of 0.05; hence, the null hypothesis was not rejected. This implies that there is no significant interaction effect of instructional strategies and sex on mathematics students’ academic achievement in Delta Central Senatorial District.

The first finding shows that there was a significant difference in mean achievement score of mathematics students taught using Peer Teaching (PT) and Inquiry-Based Teaching (IBT) strategies in Delta Central Senatorial District with those taught using Peer Teaching (PT) strategy achieving higher score than those taught using Inquiry-Based Teaching (IBT) strategy and those in the control group. This difference may be attributed to the inherent characteristics of each instructional method. Peer-Teaching may have promoted collaborative learning, allowing students to benefit from shared knowledge and peer explanations, while Inquiry-Based Teaching may have fostered curiosity, critical thinking, and self-discovery. The significant difference could imply that one method led to deeper conceptual understanding among students. This finding is in line with Uyim, and Nonye (2019) who emphasized that students learn better when actively involved in the teaching-learning process. It also agrees with findings by Osondu (2021) who reported that the use of learner-centred methods such as peer-teaching and inquiry-based approaches significantly improve students' academic achievement in mathematics.

The second finding shows that there was no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught mathematics using the peer-teaching strategy. This suggests that the peer teaching method provides an equal learning opportunity for both genders, allowing male and female students to benefit equally from collaborative and interactive instruction. This result is consistent with the findings of Uyim, and Nonye (2019) who observed that sex had no significant impact on students' achievement in mathematics when learner-centered strategies were used. It also aligns with the results of Osondu (2021) who found that sex does not significantly influence achievement when students are actively engaged in peer-assisted learning. The study also showed that there was no significant difference in the achievement scores of male and female students taught mathematics using Inquiry-Based Teaching (IBT) strategy. This suggests that the IBT method supports equitable engagement and achievement across gender, providing both male and female students equal opportunities for exploration, questioning, and problem-solving. The result also aligns with the study of Eze (2022), which reported that both boys and girls benefited equally from inquiry-oriented instructional approaches however, this disagreed with the findings of Issaka (2020) who found that sex had influence on science and mathematics achievement when inquiry-based or discovery methods were used.

Lastly, finding from the study shows that there is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of urban and rural students taught using Inquiry-Based Teaching strategy. This may be due to the nature of inquiry-based instruction, which emphasizes independent thinking and discovery rather than reliance on external resources or environment. Students in both urban and rural settings may have had equal opportunity to engage with the content through guided inquiry. This finding agrees with Salami (2022) who found that location did not significantly affect students' achievement when innovative and student-centered instructional strategies were used. It also supports the position of Aguele (2004), who argued that modern teaching strategies can bridge the urban-rural learning gap.

Conclusion/Policy Recommendations

Based on the findings from the study, it was concluded that Peer Teaching (PT) strategy was more effective than Inquiry-Based Teaching (IBT) strategy, as students taught using PT had higher achievement scores. Furthermore, the study shows that sex and location had no significant effect on students' achievement when each instructional strategy was applied independently. The researcher therefore recommends that mathematics teachers should be encouraged to adopt Peer Teaching and Inquiry-Based Teaching strategies, especially Peer Teaching, as it has proven to be more effective in enhancing students' academic achievement in mathematics. These strategies should be deliberately incorporated into classroom practice to promote active learning, peer interaction, and deeper understanding of mathematical concepts.

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